

Open Data Landscape: Repository Usage of the Swiss Research Community: Description of collection, collected data, and analysis methods

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Abstract: This article summarizes the process of data collection and data preprocessing of the Open Data Repository Landscape Survey, and provides a simple descriptive analysis of the data collected.

By embedding the data in the respective scientific disciplines and applied scientific methods, a complete overview of the current Open Data practices in Switzerland can be obtained. A more in-depth analysis of the interactions between disciplines, methods and the Open Data practices of scientists will be provided in a follow-up paper (von der Heyde, 2019b). This paper documents the study design and the process of data preprocessing. It thus describes methods that are largely independent of the results and interpretations of the data. This contribution forms the basis for reusing the dataset in other scientific projects.

Overall, 2,487 Swiss scientists participated in the survey (13.5% of all 18,367 invited). They were interviewed in an online questionnaire about their handling (data sharing practice and data reuse). The preprocessing included anonymization, plausibility check, as well as dataset selection. Anonymization was applied to 61 records. Overall 330 records were corrected, very often for the selection of the scientific discipline. Since the bepress taxonomy was quite extensive, about 10% of the participants did not find their discipline and gave verbal responses which could be used to provide disciplinary information. After these plausibility measures, the data selection was applied. In total 96 data records without any data were excluded, and 7 records needed to be excluded for various other reasons (total excluded = 103 records). In consequence, a total of 2,384 data records were available for analysis after the quality assurance measures were applied.

The preprocessing and self-evaluation of the survey also revealed minor shortcomings in the survey design. In addition to the problematic selection process for the bepress discipline taxonomy, participants expected additional scientific methods to be present. However, the examples given in the verbal responses revealed the inability to distinguish between discipline, method, and technologies used. Further, the survey design included a rather abstract catalog of options in the sections asking about repository services needed in the future. The level of competency in the broad scientific community was not sufficient to make use of the given selections. On the contrary, the section aroused some critical comments on the incomplete definition of terms.

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1 Scientific design of the survey

The survey design contained two levels, as displayed in Figure 1: For participants with little or no data sharing and reuse experience, the specific section on repositories and their services was replaced by a common section on known data sharing websites.

Figure 1: The survey design contained two stages: A short general route and a longer expert route.

1.1 General level: general disposition to share and reuse data

The first, general level mirrors the catalog validated and used by Y. Kim and various colleagues (see below). The level of abstraction is fit to be understood by scientists from all disciplines. The survey is structured around these items:

- Scientific discipline following the bepress taxonomy (Warner, 2018).
- Scientific method based on a newly derived catalog.
- Context of the specific discipline (research climate, commercial and cultural value)
- Context of the specific scientist (primary methods, research activity, maturity of scientific career)
- Perceived usefulness of data sharing and reuse
- Major challenges in data sharing and reuse
- Perceived effort of data sharing and reuse
- Availability of internal resources for data sharing and reuse
- Intention to share and reuse data Knowledge of and compliance with policies for data sharing and reuse

The bepress taxonomy was presented in a two level approach: After the top most level (10 options) level 2 and 3 were listed on one (sometimes rather long) page. The elegant solution adjusting the selection based on typed fragments of the discipline, was tested, but technically not feasible with the chosen web platform (SurveyMonkey).

The list of methods was based on the catalogs of NCRM for the sociological methods, work by Vessey, Ramesh, and Glass for the (computational methods), Alison Jane Pickard (for the philosophical methods), and Wikipedia.

General questions about the participant (scientific discipline, age, academic degree) were also included by (Y. Kim, 2016, 2017b; Y. Kim & Yoon, 2017; Yoon & Kim, 2017), as well as (Y. Kim & Stanton, 2012, 2016) Kim and Stanton. They used no extensive catalog, but asked for free descriptions and recoded those into about 10-12 top level categories. The questions regarding ethnic background were replaced; instead, the level of scientific activity and primary research method were assessed. Most people know, e.g., their h-index on Google Scholar, ResearchGate or other platforms, or their number of peer reviewed publications in 2016 and 2017.

1.2 Repository specific level: specific experiences with repositories

For those participants who were willing to contribute more time and also those who judge their expertise to be above average, a second level of the survey was offered. In this part we addressed:

- Amount of effort made in data sharing.
- Volume of data shared.
- Details about specific data repositories used in the past:
 - Reference / name
 - Primary usage (repository is known | was used for storage | was used for retrieval)
 - Services used for sharing and reuse, as well as services expected to be offered in the future
- Usefulness of metadata.
- References to knowledge bases or community archives which potentially can be developed into ORD repositories.

1.3 Validation of questionnaire

The actual questions and answer selections were mainly selected from prior work by the following:

- interview survey 2009–2010 (Wallis, Rolando, & Borgman, 2013)
- survey on data sharing 2012 (Y. Kim, 2016) evaluated in (Y. Kim, 2017a; Y. Kim & Stanton, 2013, 2016; Y. Kim & Zhang, 2015)
- survey on data sharing and reuse 2009/2010 and 2013/2014 (J. Kim, Schuler, & Pechenina, 2017)
- websurvey on the Wiley database users (Ferguson, 2014)
- survey on data reuse (Y. Kim, 2017b) evaluated in (Y. Kim & Yoon, 2017; Yoon & Kim, 2017)
- survey on data sharing and reuse (Fecher, Friesike, & Hebing, 2015; Hebing, 2016)
- survey on open data on figshare (Treadway et al., 2016)
- survey on data literacy: EU wide project (Enwald, Kortelainen, & Huotari, 2017)
- survey on personality in connection with data sharing (Linek, Fecher, Friesike, & Hebing, 2017)
- Knowledge Exchange survey (Goldstein, 2017)
- Survey on IT Governance in Germany by von der Heyde and Breiter, 2018 – evaluation in progress

- As many questions as possible were kept in synchrony with the other survey in the project (von der Heyde, 2019a).

For their 2012 survey on data sharing, Y. Kim et al. in their various publications also refer to numerous sources to validate their questions: Davis et al., 1989; Thompson, Higgins, and Howell, 1991; Taylor and Todd., 1995; McLure, Wasko, and Faraj, 2000; Kostova and Roth, 2002; Featherman and Pavlou, 2003; Pavlou, 2003; Teo et al., 2003; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Ajzen and Fishbein, 2005; Bock et al., 2005; and Limayem et al., 2007.

For their 2015 survey on data reuse, Y. Kim et al. refer in addition to numerous sources to validate their questions: Wasko and Faraj, 2000; Bock, Zmud, Kim, and Lee, 2005; Son and Benbasat, 2007; and Kim and Stanton, 2016.

The questions were selected on the basis of expected relevance for the overall project. Indicators not showing significant results in prior work were excluded, unless other evidence pointed towards beneficial outcomes. The indicators (mainly from all Y. Kim et al. publications) were reduced to the most relevant factor of the PCAs reported in the publications.

Most data from the studies above is available and will be compared to the results of this survey in follow-up papers.

1.4 Validity of the sample

Following the arguments of (Y. Kim & Yoon, 2017) with reference to (Babbie, 1998) we compare the first and last 20% of the response of our survey to detect any order effects or abnormalities. Due to the two-phase design, we tagged the 20% responses of the start of the first invitation phase, 20% of the end (just before the reminder), the 20% after the reminder and 20% at the end of the survey; all others were tagged as “other”.

In a brief screening of the dataset, we found only few variables and questions, which showed slight effects: sharing in institutional repositories and data journals; reasons for not sharing: lack of founding and time; endorsed respective signed three of the major policies (OECD, Force, Allea); the altruistic attitude towards reuse; willingness to participate in part two declined linearly; status of the participant: Maximum of Prof. were observed in late first phase; the maximum of postdocs participated late in second phase after the reminder. Finally, the evaluation differed in two factors – see chapter 6.1.

Overall the number of effects was so small and more than 90% of the variables showed no order effect. Therefore, we restrain from counter measures for non-biased responses. Evaluating the above variables should be done with care, nonetheless.

2 Implementation, distribution and response rate

The survey was implemented as a web-based questionnaire using the commercial platform SurveyMonkey¹. The questionnaire was published as supplementary material as both a PDF and as a JSON export from the cloud platform. The survey implementation was piloted with a small group of volunteers distinct from the actual target group.

¹ Software for online questionnaires developed by the SVKM Inc. See description at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SurveyMonkey>.

Participation in the study was possible from Sep. 11th 2018 to Oct. 3rd 2018. The data collected on SurveyMonkey will be deleted from that platform at the end of the project.

Various information channels were used to invite participants to the study. The first invitation took place on Sep. 11th at 13:00 CET. A reminder of participation was sent out on Sep. 26th. The reminder was also used to communicate the intended closing date, October 1st. Since responses kept coming in, on Oct. 2nd a notice was added to the introduction page about the upcoming end of the survey. On Oct 3rd, the survey access pages were finally closed at 7:00 CET.

The invitation to participate was sent out as follows:

- SNSF: E-mail with invitation text in the preferred language (German, English, French) to 16,811 persons:
 - all successful applicants (Swiss scientists) from the last 3 years (since 2015) who are currently funded by the SNSF.
 - all applicants (Swiss scientists) from the last year (since 2017)
- SAGW: Forwarding of the invitation by e-mail to 908 scientists in the field of Swiss academies.
- swissuniversities, KUB, FID: Forwarding of the invitation by e-mail to an unknown number of networked decision-makers who could each address their network.

Response rates across all channels are given in Table 1 and are displayed in Figure 2.

Channel	Number of participants	Invitations 11. Sep. 2018	Bounced	Delivered	Reminders 26. Sep. 2018	Bounced	Delivered	Response Rate
SNSF-de	1012	7829	223	7606	7688	86	7602	13.3%
SNSF-fr	566	4180	195	3985	4121	138	3983	14.2%
SNSF-en	439	5450	230	5220	5325	108	5217	8.4%
swiss-universities	433							
SAGW	21	908						2.3%
FID	10							
KUB	6							
Sum	2487	18367						13.5%

Table 1: Distribution channels of the survey and corresponding response rates. The second column is also displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Response rates across channels.

3 Export of data records

The dataset was exported from SurveyMonkey in both CSV and xlsx formats. 2,487 records were exported.

Initial analyses and data cleaning routines were performed in Microsoft Excel (Version 2010) up to the point of data exclusion. Further analyses were performed in JMP² (Version 13.0).

4 Quality assurance

4.1 Anonymization

The data was collected anonymously as far as possible. However, names, ORCID, web links and other information which directly indicated the respondent were provided by 61 respondents in the free text fields. This information was first evaluated (example from the index) and then removed from the data record.

Before publication, the last comments — respondents' opinion on the survey — were removed. These comments were submitted in a document to the contracting authority of the survey (SNSF and swissuniversities) for further evaluation without reference to the creators.

4.2 Plausibility criteria

Data were corrected if:

- I. Specifications were made in the free text fields that directly corresponded to a response option which was not selected.
 - a. Pages 2-4:
 - i. Deleted 131 "Other" responses and changed or moved to specific discipline.
 - ii. Changed selection of second disciplinary area corresponding to the selection of sub-discipline(s): 133
 - iii. Removed redundant identical second selection for 106 cases
 - b. Pages 5-14 (Selection of second level bepress discipline taxonomy option):
 - i. Added the specific "Other" response which had been removed from pages 2 and 3 as described above: 109
 - ii. Checked additional options based on "other" from pages 2/3: 114
 - c. Page 18, question 1 (How have you shared data?) for some data given in "Other":
 - i. "no data was shared" → checked option "For some projects no data was shared" (21)
 - ii. Mention of a general repository → checked option "Through a general-purpose data repository (e.g., Zenodo, Dryad, git, etc.)" (8)
 - iii. Mention of a disciplinary repository → checked option "Through a discipline-specific data repository" (5)
 - d. Page 24, question 3 ("Current academic status"):
 - i. PhD, doctoral student → checked option "Graduate Student" (20)
 - ii. All "Ambizione" → checked option "Post-Doctoral Fellow" (4)

² Software for statistical analysis developed by the SAS Institute. See description at: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JMP_\(statistical_software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JMP_(statistical_software)).

- iii. Unchecked “Prefer not to disclose” when other options were used (2)
- iv. “Other” → Checked options for staff, researchers or professors according to dataset (9)

In total, 593 changes were made to the selection of the disciplines. Overall, 11,870 data points were collected in the discipline selection section; thus, about 5% of the data needed corrections.

In all other parts of the questionnaire a total of 115 changes took place. This amounts to changes to 0.078% of the total of 147,071 data points collected.

Overall, data from 330 participants were changed, of which 263 cases (10.6% of 2,487 participant records) needed changes in the discipline selection. For 81 participants (3.25% of 2,487 participant records), changes were made only in questions not regarding the disciplines.

In total 2,157 (86.7%) datasets did not require correction by these plausibility checks.

4.3 Criteria for the exclusion of records

Data records were excluded after the successful plausibility check according to the following rules:

1. If no substantial data was contained: 96 (2 without any data, 94 with only the first question answered) - mean time spent on the survey for those excluded was 0 min 48 sec.
2. If data were very inconsistent or showed other particular peculiarities:
 - a. Obvious random patterns of answers: 2 (Z1541) 32 disciplines + rest of survey in 10 min; (Z1183) random data indicated in publications, near constant data in most ratings, inconsistent indications for sharing variables, time to complete survey 8:10 min.
 - b. Destructive, vandalising contributions in the free text fields: 1 (Z418)
 - c. Direct indication of unfit or random answers. These comments will not be published as this was foreseen in the study design: 3 (Z639, Z1095, Z1242)
 - d. Duplicate entries, probably due to resumption of response at a later date and technical malfunction (=reassignment) of a subscriber number: 2 (Z1042=Z1043; Z1354=Z1390). The older data record was excluded because the newer one was completed more fully.

4.4 Summary of the data preprocessing procedure

Overall, the quality assurance measures can be summarized as follows:

- Number of records in export: 2,487, of which 61 records were anonymized
- Records corrected after plausibility checking: 330 (2,157 remained unchanged)
- Records excluded for containing very little data (criterion 1): 96
Records excluded for other reasons (criterion 2): 8
- Total records, after plausibility check and exclusion: 2,383 (=100% of the data used for analysis)

Please note: Although the 2,384 data records remaining after plausibility checking and exclusion will be used for further analysis in follow-up work, this paper continues to look at the original set of 2,487 records.

5 Evaluation of the study itself

In order to enable others to validate and trust the results of this study, the survey is evaluated and described in the following paragraphs outside the actual scientific content.

5.1 Completion rate

The participants completed the questionnaire with varying degrees of intensity. Since no question was obligatory, the participants could leave single questions or pages unanswered. Consequently, the number of respondents varies per question (see Figure 3).

In general the participants gave answers on almost all pages they have reviewed. Most of the difference between the number of participants still in the survey at a certain page and the number of answers was due to the page logic which enabled most participants to progress faster through the survey.

Figure 3: We have plotted the number of answers and number of participants per page of the survey. We evaluated, if participants skipped pages due to the page logic or answered later pages to determine the last page per participant.

Figure 4: Number of datasets with a certain number of pages completed

There were 165 questions on the 48 pages, but not all of them were shown to the participants due to branching during the survey. Depending on the participants' answers, several different routes could be taken.

Complete participation for respondents with little experience in data sharing and reuse required 17 pages, without the evaluation page at the end. A typical participation including the second part of the study required 28 pages. The theoretical maximum required 40 pages. The de facto maximum was 34 pages, which only a few participants completed.

266 participants who judged their experience with respect to data sharing and reuse to be above the average of their colleagues within the same discipline were branched into the longer survey route automatically. Another 73 decided to voluntarily take the longer route after having been prompted. Overall, 339 participants answered the second, more detailed part of the survey.

Figure 5: Cumulative number of datasets across completed pages

The SurveyMonkey survey tool provided a prediction for participation in the study. Accordingly, a completion rate of 44% for an average duration of 37min was to be expected. Our own calculations had estimated duration of participation for the short alternative at 19 minutes and the more detailed part at approximately 29 minutes.

In fact, the survey achieved a completion rate of 62% with an average length of stay on the survey pages of about 15 minutes.

Figure 6: Overall duration of participation for participants completing a specific number of pages. Data records with answers on 0 or 1 pages were excluded from the survey after quality control.

The total duration (actual end time minus start time) including interruptions when the participant was not working on the survey is shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 for all 2,326 datasets below 120 minutes total. The other 161 datasets (=6.5%) showed considerably longer completion times. We assume respondents did not actually spend this entire time on completing of the survey, but just left the browser open and continued the survey after some other tasks.

Figure 7: Histogram of the duration of participation (up to 120 minutes).

6 Descriptive statistics

The survey closed with evaluations question about the survey itself to assess survey fatigue, workload, comments and recommendations. Since the target audience were scientists from all disciplinary fields, methodological advice was also expected.

6.1 Evaluative responses of participants

The participants were generous in giving additional comments in the “other” sections of the survey questionnaire. Overall, 1,137 comments were given. Including free text questions on

names of data repositories and the h-index, 2,350 text responses were provided by 755 participants.

Overall statistics on different categories of responses are shown in Table 2.

Abs. Count	Percent	Topic
52	2.1%	Criticism of how survey was done (methodological level)
81	3.3%	Criticism of survey goals / missing perspective
46	1.8%	Comment / criticism addressed directly to SNSF
85	3.4%	Criticism of data sharing / management
32	1.3%	No data: discipline / scientist does not produce data
41	1.6%	Different concept of data
47	1.9%	Otherwise (unspecific) not relevant for discipline
18	0.7%	Positive Encouragement
64	2.6%	Remarkable / constructive contribution
3	0.1%	Vandalism / random answers
57	2.3%	Options not known / level of competency
51	2.1%	Question-specific criticism
21	0.8%	Asking for more definitions of terms
33	1.3%	Questions / answers are N/A
118	4.7%	General comments
62	2.5%	General criticism
964	38.8%	Contribution as additional option or text

Table 2: Categorization of text comments and free text answers

The categorical analysis of the evaluation is shown in Figure 8. Minor effects exists for two variables:

- 1) `Eval_Policy` described if the survey should help to establish good policies by the SNSF. The rates for agreement were high for participants reacting fast in both phases (initial and reminder). Also the reminder showed higher agreement to the statement in general. This coincides with having more biology disciplines within these participants.
- 2) `Eval_Difficult` describes how difficulty of the questions was rated. Participants being later rated higher. This coincides with more social scientists being among these.

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		Freq Share Rate	Eval_							Total Responses	Total Cases	Total Cases Responding
			Helps to establish policies	Waste of time	High burden to me	Happy to have contributed	Appropriate for the purpose	Questions were difficult				
OrderCategory	FirstPhase1	80	16	21	107	68	41	333	381	195		
		24,0%	4,8%	6,3%	32,1%	20,4%	12,3%					
	LastPhase1	79	17	18	106	81	52	353	381	208		
		22,4%	4,8%	5,1%	30,0%	22,9%	14,7%					
	FirstReminder	107	11	14	124	92	49	397	386	225		
		27,0%	2,8%	3,5%	31,2%	23,2%	12,3%					
	LastReminder	114	10	20	138	90	73	445	392	242		
		25,6%	2,2%	4,5%	31,0%	20,2%	16,4%					
	Others	214	26	34	247	188	114	823	844	472		
		26,0%	3,2%	4,1%	30,0%	22,8%	13,9%					
25,4%		3,1%	4,0%	29,3%	22,3%	13,5%						

Test Each Response, Poisson

OrderCategory, Eval_

Eval_	ChiSquare	Prob>ChiSq
Helps to establish policies	9,1480	0,0575
Waste of time	3,3375	0,5030
High burden to me	2,2852	0,6835
Happy to have contributed	5,1006	0,2771
Appropriate for the purpose	3,9972	0,4064
Questions were difficult	9,1193	0,0582

Chi-squared tests use Poisson rates.

Test Each Response, Binomial

OrderCategory, Eval_

Eval_	ChiSquare	Prob>ChiSq
Helps to establish policies	12,1393	0,0163*
Waste of time	3,4571	0,4844
High burden to me	2,3934	0,6638
Happy to have contributed	7,3985	0,1163
Appropriate for the purpose	5,0578	0,2814
Questions were difficult	10,6645	0,0306*

Assuming multiple responses are Check All That Apply (CATA).

Figure 8: Categorical analysis of the evaluation of the survey.

6.2 Demographic overview of the participants

The demographic distributions were in the expected range (see Figure 9). Of the respondents who indicated their age (n=1,636), a balance between young (25-39 years old) and more senior (40-64 years old) scientists was observed. As for the gender distribution, there were approximately twice as many male participants as female participants (n=1,630).

Figure 9: Gender and age distribution of the participants.

The distributions of current academic positions (n=1,870) across gender and age were observed as expected. The majority of professors were male, in contrast to younger academics, where males and females are nearly equally represented in the survey (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Distribution of current academic positions by gender.

As expected, professors were in general often older, whereas graduate students and post-doctoral fellows were often younger (see Figure 11).

The response rate of the main target group (Professor) was virtually identical to the overall response rate of 13.5% of all invited people: The BFS statistics indicate a total of about 4,370 professors for Switzerland. The participating 587 professors amount to a response rate of 13.4%. For all other groups, the response rates are much below in comparison to the total numbers in Switzerland.

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Figure 11: Distribution of academic positions by age.

6.3 Selection of Disciplines

Overall, 11,562 selections of single disciplines were provided by the 2,487 participants. On average, this amounts to 4.6 disciplines per participant. The distribution of the number of selected disciplines is displayed in Figure 12. Most of the respondents selected 7 disciplines.

Figure 12: Number of scientists who chose their disciplines from the bepress taxonomy. Note that the 96 participants who did not answer more than the first page of the questionnaire thus did not provide a completed discipline selection.

6.4 Selection of Methods

In total, 11,835 methods were selected by 2,292 respondents (about 4.75 on average). Most respondents selected three research methods (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Histogram of number of different methods selected by the participants.

195 participants did not indicate a method (including the 96 who had already dropped out at or prior to) the stage of indicating their discipline. Surprisingly, selection of two methods was less frequent than selection of one method. It is possible that several of the participants who had decided to select one method had not realized it was possible to select multiple methods.

In total, 130 participants provided additional methods under “Other”. Of these, only 20 respondents did not select any of the given methods. This could be seen as an indication of the overall acceptability of the catalog, covering most methods used by the scientists in the participating disciplines.

6.5 Mentioned Repositories

Overall, 205 of the 2,487 participants mentioned having used a specific repository³. Of these, only 182 named a specific repository they had used in the section that asked for it. The other repositories mentioned were extracted from 23 participants’ general comments on the survey. The given 290 items were extracted and categorized (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Result of the categorization process: sum and number counts of the names repositories which turned out not always to match the intended criterion.

Overall, 8 general purpose repositories and 17 discipline specific repositories as well as 6 OA library repositories mentioned more than once as shown in Figure 15. In addition 71 were mentioned exactly once. The ambiguous mentions of NCBI without a specific repository was counted but could not be attributed to a repository as ENA/Pride/BioSample were mentioned otherwise specifically.

³ As most people gave this information in the second part of the survey, it is important to remember that only 339 participants participated in that part.

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Figure 15: Frequency of repositories specifically mentioned.

7 Supplementary Material

Extensive supplementary material will be provided on Zenodo⁴ in conjunction with this data paper (von der Heyde, 2019c):

- Questionnaire as PDF: All questions in the appearance of the online format.
- Questionnaire as JSON: Export of SurveyMonkey cloud platform including all options.
- Questionnaire in xlsx Format: this includes references to other surveys using identical or near-identical questions.
- Anonymized raw data (CSV, xlsx).
- Final plausibility checked data (CSV, xlsx).
- Additional analytical data sheet for text, biometrics and other indicators.
- bepress taxonomy in xlsx format including mappings to DFG and SNSF catalogs.

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